

It's Okay to be Not Okay: Lived Experiences of Multigrade School Teacher-In-Charge in Laak North District

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Abstract. A multigrade school teacher-in-charge serves dual roles as school head and classroom teacher in multigrade schools, leaving them with challenging tasks in overseeing the school and managing multigrade classrooms. The study aimed to explore the experiences of these teachers, understand their strategies in handling their dual roles, and design a capability training series based on the needs of multigrade teachers. A qualitative phenomenological research approach was employed with five multigrade school teacher-in-charge as participants, selected based on purposive sampling techniques. Research instruments included the interview schedule and interview guide which underwent validation and pilot-testing. Data was collected through iterative in-depth interview while focus group discussion with the same participants was done for data verification and reflexivity. Thematic analysis of data applied Colaizzi's method. Notably, the study revealed major thematic findings: community partnership and cultural responsiveness, teacher competence, student-centered management, collaborative community leadership, efficiency in multitasking and problem-solving, adaptive leadership, challenges in multigrade teaching, importance of teacher collaboration and dedication, and empowerment of school leaders in multigrade education. Moreover, the study uncovered strategies employed by multigrade school teacher-in-charge, including data-informed leadership, monitoring techniques for managing schools, strategic planning, financial tactics for resource management, and research initiatives in multigrade education. The study recommends implementing a capability training series to address the complexities of managing multigrade schools. Adoption of the training series can effectively tackle the unique challenges faced by teachers in multigrade educational settings.

Introduction

Multigrade schools across the world are still prevalent nowadays due to the high demand for education, especially in far-flung areas (Naparan and Alinsug, 2021). These multigrade schools are led mainly by teachers-in-charge. Multigrade school teacher-in-charge is a designation function in multigrade schools, serving as a school head and classroom teacher (Tayoni and Abocejo, 2023).

They ought to perform the duties of being a teacher-in-charge as mentioned by (Erdem and Kalender (2021), such as managing the school resources and mentoring teachers, and as multigrade classroom teachers, such as instructing students. They also added that the teacher's function as school head manifests in the experiences of multigrade school teacher-in-charge, which seem doubly heavier than other school heads.

In Kiruhura District, Uganda, Kyayemagye and Kintu (2020) stated that multigrade school teacher-in-charge in multigrade schools juggle two roles: teaching in the classroom and leading the school. The lack of sufficient leadership training and experience poses a major challenge, hindering their ability to effectively manage the school. In India, Bajpai & Pandey (2023) revealed that geographic isolation and low enrollment rates per grade level result in one teacher assuming both classroom instruction and administrative roles, leading to a significant burden.

In the Philippine context, the challenges faced by multigrade school teacher-in-charge are a common reality, reflecting the broader struggles experienced within the context of multigrade schools. According to Naparan and Castañeda (2021), the most common problems of multigrade school teacher-in-charge in multigrade schools are instructional preparation, instructional materials, classroom management supervision, schemes for teaching multigrade classes, application of teaching methodology in real teaching-learning situations, lack of school facilities, schedule of activities, poor working conditions of teachers, inadequate pre-and in-service training of teachers related to multigrade teaching.

Meanwhile, in the Division of Davao de Oro, Laak North District has the greatest number of multigrade schools, headed mainly by a teacher-in-charge (TIC). In fact, according to the data from the consolidated report of multigrade district coordinators of the Division of Davao de Oro in 2022, Laak North District has 12 multigrade schools, and 5 of them are led by a teacher-in-charge. These data have drawn attention to the need to consider Laak North District as the locale

Methodology

Research Design

In this qualitative study, a phenomenological approach was utilized through the descriptive type of phenomenology. In simple terms, phenomenology seeks to describe the essence of a phenomenon by discovering it from the standpoint of those who have experienced it. Its goal is to describe the meaning of experience through what was experienced and how it was experienced (Neubauer, 2015). In connection to this, Leigh-Osroosh (2021) stated that a descriptive phenomenological study describes the participants' experiences in a most straightforward way of investigating their lived experiences. Through this design, the researcher could join the participants' environment and grasp and understand their experiences. The researcher explains and draws out the key informants' positions and thoughts.

Additionally, it is the study of phenomena. It studies the lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how people understand those experiences (Bliss, 2016). Phenomenology distinguished itself from other qualitative research by focusing on experienced meaning rather than on descriptions of overt actions and behaviors. The phenomenological approach aims to study a phenomenon as it is experienced and perceived by the participant. It explores the nature of the phenomenon rather than what causes it or why it is being experienced.

To conclude, this phenomenological study helps understand the meaning of people's lived experiences by exploring and focusing on their experience of a phenomenon. As a result, it is an appropriate design that fits the focus of this study, which is to gain a profound understanding of the lived experiences of multigrade teachers-in-charge in handling multigrade schools.

Unit of Analysis

This qualitative study delved into the lived experiences of multigrade school teacher-in-charge, focusing on the challenges and strategies encountered in leading and managing the multigrade school context. By centering on the firsthand accounts of these educators, this study had contextualized into the dynamic landscape of multigrade school environments. With this, the researcher extracted valuable insights from the lived experiences of multigrade school teacher-in-charge, facilitated the generation of thematic analyses that led to output development.

Research Participants

This study was conducted in the multigrade schools of Laak North District. Laak North District has the most multigrade schools led by a teacher-in-charge as per data report consolidated by the multigrade district coordinators from the Division of Davao de Oro. Additionally, most of the multigrade schools from Laak North District are situated in far-flung areas. The multigrade school teacher-in-charge also functioned as classroom teachers, and they were chosen based on the multigrade school they represent in Laak North District. Five multigrade school teacher-in-charge were the participants of this study.

In the selection of the participants, the researcher was guided by the following set of criteria: (1) a multigrade school teacher-in-charge who also functioned as a classroom teacher; (2) must have at least three years of teaching experience in multigrade school; (3) at least two years of experience as multigrade teacher-in-charge; and (4) willingness of the participants to be interviewed.

Moreover, this study utilized convenience sampling. Convenience sampling provides a simpler and easier way of collecting data for the researcher based on the availability and willingness of the participants (Golzar et al., 2021). The study considered five multigrade school teacher-in-charge who represented the multigrade schools in Laak North District. Alase (2017), Creswell (2007), and Creswell and Poth (2016) supported the idea that interviewing five participants could saturate the data needed for the study. In phenomenological studies, in-depth interviews with participants are often used to collect data.

Research Instruments

The research instruments used in gathering data and information to answer the research questions were the interview protocol and schedule. The researcher crafted the protocol and schedule, which were used during the in-depth interview (IDI) of the participants. This researcher-made interview protocol underscored the necessary process for conducting the interview. The interview schedule contained sets of questions based on the research questions set beforehand. Each research question set has at least three (3) sub-questions that capture the general idea of the research questions.

Moreover, the interview schedule was developed and prepared in advance to aid the researcher and investigator in gathering information or data pertaining to the topic or issue. An interview schedule is a list comprising a set of organized questions (Bearman, 2019). All the questions written in this study's interview schedule were made to be precisely like those written in the interview protocol. After preparing the two mentioned research instruments, the researcher subjected them to undergo validation with the help of a pool of experts. Three (3) validators who possessed the needed expertise and qualifications to analyze the items and provide feedback. The research instruments underwent some feedback from the validators, which were integrated accordingly by the researcher.

Subsequently, the researcher conducted a try-out of the validated research instruments with participants from another school district who were expected to possess characteristics similar to those of the actual participants of the study. These three try-out participants were from (2) Maco District and (1) Pantukan District in the Division of Davao de Oro. They also are multigrade school teacher-in-charge; two are females, and one is male. Then, the try-out data recording was evaluated by at least two (2) experts to determine whether the instruments manifested consistency and accuracy in gathering the needed data.

Data Collection Techniques

Typically, qualitative researchers employ several different approaches, collecting information from a wide variety of sources, including interviews, observations, and archival materials. In the conduct of this study, primary data sources were gathered through IDI, which was employed in an iterative process.

In-depth Interview. In phenomenological studies, interviews are typically used to collect data. It paints a fuller picture of what went down and why by placing additional information into its proper perspective. Through interviews, participants are given a voice to share their stories (Deterding and Waters, 2021). In this study, the researcher conducted a face-to-face, in-depth interview (IDI) with the selected participants in an iterative process until data saturation was achieved. Recording the interview proceeding was done with consent from the participants. Recording the whole interview is a big help to the researcher, especially during the transcription process.

The researcher also referred to secondary sources like books, journals, and articles that include a range of opinions, results, and data from various authors (Trefy, 2020) will be used to back up details and claims gathered from the interviews. Similarly, it aims to obtain opinions, perspectives, and views from the experiences of the multigrade teachers-in-charge. Therefore, these data sources are enough to achieve the participants' desired understanding of data analysis.

Focus Group Discussion. After saturating the participants' data from the in-depth interview, focus-group discussion was employed. Focus group discussion (FGD) is an extended interview method (Gundumogula, 2021). Also, FGD was employed for reflexivity, in which the gathered data were presented to the participants to validate whether the data gathered during

the in-depth interview reflected what the participants intended to convey. The researcher intended to ask about the data presented to confirm whether all formulated meanings or themes are amenable to the participants, thus avoiding researcher bias. Accordingly, reflexivity preserves the rawness and authenticity of the data gathered, neutralizing subjectivity (Olmos-Vega et al., 2023)

Data Analysis

This research employed the data analysis methodology of Colaizzi in analyzing data. The distinctive seven-step method of Colaizzi (1978) provides a thorough analysis, with each step remaining close to the results. The result is an all-encompassing yet succinct summary of the phenomenon under analysis, confirmed by the participants who created it. The methodology relies on rich first-person encounter accounts, which can come from face-to-face interviews but can also be collected in various ways: published narratives, blogs, study diaries, online interviews, etc. (Morrow et al., 2015).

First, familiarization. The researcher familiarized himself with the gathered information by reading the participants' responses several times. Second, identifying significant statements. The researcher classified all claims as aligned with the study's objectives. Third, formulating meanings. The researcher carefully considered the significant statements to adhere closely to the phenomenon being examined to establish interpretations critical to the subject of the analysis. Fourth, clustering themes. The researcher grouped the established meanings into prevalent themes across all accounts. Fifth, developing an exhaustive description. The researcher integrated all the themes generated at step by writing a complete and inclusive summary of the teacher's strategies. Sixth, producing the fundamental structure. The researcher condensed the detailed explanation into a brief and concise statement that captures the phenomenon's aspects. Seventh, seeking verification of the fundamental structure. The researcher referred to the participants' fundamental answers and statements to analyze whether the dense statements captured their impressions.

Presented in figure below is the illustration of the data analysis and its steps.

Figure No. 1 The Distinctive Seven-Step Method of Colaizzi (1978)

Role of the Researcher

In this study, the role of the researcher was to collect, analyze, and interpret the gathered data with utmost consideration for credibility, dependability, and transferability. While doing so, the participants were assured that their testimonies and identities were not shared and exposed to anyone. Name titles are assigned to each participant, with great emphasis on covering the identities of those who are interested in direct privacy.

Credibility is defined as the assurance that can be placed in the truth of the research findings (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The priority goal of this study is to gather believable results. In addressing credibility, firstly, the researcher ensured the process of selecting the participants that best apply. Secondly, in crafting the research procedure, the researcher used in-depth interviews to extract thoughts and insights on the lived experiences of the multigrade school teacher-in-charge in handling multigrade schools.

Transferability is described by Lincoln and Guba (1985) as a way of achieving a type of external validity. By describing a phenomenon, inadequate detail, one can begin to assess the extent to which conclusions are transferable to other times, settings, situations, and people. In this study, the researcher addressed transferability by including information and documents provided to capture relevant answers to the research questions that are credible and comparable to a similar situation, allowing researchers to access facilities and linkages in innovating conclusions as bases for further research study.

Dependability emphasizes the need for the researchers to account for the ever-changing context within research. The researcher is responsible for describing the changes that occur in the setting and how these changes affect the way the researcher approaches the study (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Data Gathering Procedure

In the gathering of data, this study employed a systematic procedure. First, the researcher crafted the researcher made interview guide questions. Second, the researcher submitted the crafted interview guide questions to three expert validators for face and content validation. Third, the researcher conducted pilot test through In-depth interview with use of validated interview guide question. Fourth, submitted the gathered data to the thesis adviser for validation. Afterwards, sent a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao de Oro and the District Supervisor of Laak North District, signed by the graduate school program head and thesis adviser, asking permission to conduct the study among the multigrade teacher-in-charge. Upon the approval, the researcher then sent a letter of consent to the participants. After that, the researcher scheduled a meeting with participants, gave them a copy of the in-depth interview questions, and conducted an orientation about the study, including the agreement on the date of the in-depth interview. When the in-depth interviews were completed, the researcher expressed gratitude to the participants by giving them tokens. Afterward, the data are collected, interpreted, and analyzed confidentially and accordingly.

Ethical Considerations

Along with constructing this study, the researcher also considered the ethical issues to establish the study's trustworthiness. These ethical issues were considered to ensure the security and safety of the participants, data, and the study's credibility.

Confidentiality towards the results and findings, including safeguarding the participants and coding system, was exercised. Codes were used to hide and protect the identity of the participants. Hence, the researcher maintained the gathered information in secrecy and valued confidentiality.

Respect for the person is an obligation of the researcher not to exploit the research participants' weaknesses and to consider the responses and decisions of those involved seriously. The researcher also obtained agreements or permissions from the institution and the participants and situated the participants to choose freely and understand what is at stake in their involvement.

Objectivity means the willingness and ability to examine evidence dispassionately (Nahrin, 2015). In this study, the researcher remained neutral and did not induce any personal biases or feelings in the interpretation of data. The researcher did not fabricate, falsify, or misrepresent data. Reflexivity was employed after the data gathered to avoid partialities and biases from the participants through presenting them the results of the study.

Justice requires a reasonable allocation of the risks and benefits as research results. It is defined as the ethical obligation to distribute the benefits and burdens of research fairly. It pertains to the right to fair treatment and relates to the researcher treating those who decline to participate in a study fairly without prejudice (Barrow et al., 2020). Hence, the researcher took responsibility for ensuring ethical consideration. It is essential to acknowledge all the participants' contributions as they are generally part of the success of the research. They are given due credit in all their endeavors and should not be exploited for personal gain. Also, the participants did not spend any amount during the interview. Sensible tokens were given to them as a sign of recognition for their efforts in the study's success.

The researcher observed respect for intellectual property. In doing so, the researcher gave credit to the authors and researchers from the studies and articles used as references. The researcher also honored copyrights and other forms of intellectual property and avoided plagiarism. Lastly, the researcher did not go beyond personal matters and respected the participants in sharing their experiences and strategies. The researcher also observed proper attitudes and ethics when facing participants or conducting interviews.

Results and Discussion

Major Themes	Clustered Themes	Core Ideas
Empowerment in Multigrade School Leadership	Enhancing Leadership Skills for Multigrade School Management	Having limited leadership background in managing a multigrade school Possessing limited experience in leading a multigrade school
	Inspiring Teachers and Meeting Community Demands	Striving to inspire teachers and address community needs Aiming to motivate teachers and meet community needs
	Discovering Joy Amidst Weariness	Finding enjoyment amidst fatigue Having the happiness to move forward despite of challenges
	Remaining Steadfast in the Face of Challenges	Dealing with challenges head-on Treating challenges in a positive way
	Juggling Teaching Preparation and Leadership Duties	Balancing teaching preparation and leadership responsibilities Handling dual responsibilities simultaneously

Table No. 1 Major Theme: Empowerment in Multigrade School Leadership

Empowerment in Multigrade School Leadership

Multigrade school teachers-in-charge in Laak North District have developed leadership traits being a school head. From leading the community, colleagues, and to students. Their daily experiences empowered them to strive and improve their leadership to their respective school. This major theme revolves from five clustered themes such as: enhancing leadership skills for multigrade school management; inspiring teachers and meeting community demands; discovering joy amidst weariness; remaining steadfast in the face of challenges; and juggling teaching preparation and leadership duties. It discussed how their determination made them stronger to continue leading and teaching a multigrade school.

The primary duty of the multigrade school teacher-in-charge as stated by Thaba-Nkadimene et al. (2019) that it revolves around improving the learning standards within the school, thereby securing its overall success. This objective necessitates robust leadership, wherein the principal plays a pivotal role in guaranteeing the provision of high-quality education.

Enhancing Leadership Skills for Multigrade School Management.

Given the situation of being a multigrade school teacher-in-charge, the participants honestly confessed their struggles with their leadership skills, especially in leading in a multigrade school context. This clustered theme is focused on and based on the core ideas of having limited leadership background in managing a multigrade school and possessing limited experience in leading a multigrade school. This entails that these multigrade school teachers-in-charge in Laak North District lack experience, knowledge, or training when it comes to leading a multigrade school.

In connection to this, Participant 1-Genesis shared how limited his knowledge or experience in leading a multigrade school is. He confessed:

"Ahm as a school head kulang gihapon sa ko ug background with regards to leadership ug dealing with in leading a school, especially in multigrade school..." (IDI-1)

Also, Participant 4-Numbers confirmed:

"Lisod kaayo nga isip usa ka school as teacher-in-charge nga isabak dayon sa pag lead sa usa ka multigrade school without prior knowledge." (IDI-4)

With this, Jimenez and Galicia (2023) stated that multigrade school teacher-in-charge devoted considerable effort to fostering relationships and trust among teachers, students, and parents. Truth be told, this discloses the real scenarios and experiences of multigrade school teacher-in-charge back to their respective multigrade schools. In the long run, Prastiawan et al. (2020) said that effective leadership within organizations is essential for achieving goals and guiding others in task completion. A well-functioning organization relies on school leaders who possess genuine and effective leadership qualities. It is crucial for multigrade school teacher-in-charge to embody traits that align with established standards of leadership.

Inspiring Teachers and Meeting Community Demands.

Multigrade school teacher-in-charge played an important role in managing a multigrade school because of their multiple supervisory and instructional responsibilities need to be executed. Their effectivity reflects on how they inspire their teachers and address community needs. This clustered theme was based on the core ideas of striving to inspire teachers and address community needs and aiming to motivate teachers and meet community needs. They inspire because they want their teachers to show consistency in teaching multigrade while meeting community demands to make the community feel that they are being cared of.

This means that these multigrade school teacher-in-charge in Laak North District really made sure that they performed their function as a leader/school head. It is a vital role of multigrade teacher-in-charge to look after the development of their colleagues and community.

In association with, Participant 2-Exodus shared how important it is to inspire his teachers and meet community needs. He revealed:

...maningkamot as school head ah maningkamot ko sa teacher para ma inspire pud sila nya mga community ako nalang pud gikuan gi ahh gi tan aw ilang mga needs para ma kuan ko sa ilaha didto makita nako ang ilang kuan kinahanglanon.(IDI-2)

Participant 1-Genesis added:

"Kabalo ta dapat mudala sa atong mga teachers kay sila permi ang naa sa skwelahan para mag serbisyo sa mga Kabataan." (IDI-1)

Pertaining to the response of Participant 2, the multigrade school teacher-in-charge in Laak North District really understood every detail of their job roles. Linked to this, Ansley et al. (2019) supposed that inspiring colleagues boosts the morale of the teachers and meets community needs as well. They fully grasp nothing but to inspire teachers and look after the community's needs. For this reason, Wang et al. (2022) emphasized that these multigrade school teachers-in-charge have a vision of influencing and inspiring their colleagues. Besides, they have a pivotal role in upholding school-community connections.

Discovering Joy Amidst Weariness.

Considering the heavy role of multigrade school teacher-in-charge, still they manage to find joy despite of setbacks and struggles in leading a multigrade school. This clustered theme was derived from the core ideas which are finding enjoyment amidst fatigue and having the happiness to move forward despite of challenges. This idea implicates that multigrade school teacher-in-charge manage to see the positive side of their job roles despite of fatigue.

In conjunction with, Participant 3-Leviticus shared his thoughts and emotions as to what is felt in finding joy to become a multigrade school teacher-in-charge. She joyfully said:

"Mura syag, kanang akong ma feel no kay mura syag roller coaster ride, enjoy nga kapoy..." (IDI-3)

Participant 2- Exodus also expressed:

"Luyo sa kakapoy ug kahago, malipayon man gihapon ang kinabuhi sa usa ka multigrade school teacher-in-charge." (IDI-2)

Through that, Cronqvist (2021) stated that finding delight in work being multigrade school teacher-in-charge is connected to the environment in which learning takes place and is felt when teachers and community feel secured, appreciated, and respected. Truly, realizing the importance of being a school head made them realize that being a multigrade school teacher-in-charge is worth having. Hence, Mag, Sinfield, Burns, and Abegglen (2021) declared that experiencing joy in leading a multigrade school equips multigrade school teacher-in-charge in Laak North District with the necessary tools and resources to transform their approach, making it more appealing and fulfilling endeavor. This positive shift also influences students, teachers, and community as they commit to engage in the improvement of the multigrade school.

Remaining Steadfast in the Face of Challenges.

Challenges of multigrade school teacher-in-charge are indeed inevitable. These challenges sometimes caused them exhausted, physically tired, and mentally drained. This clustered theme was drawn from the core ideas which are dealing with challenges head-on and treating challenges in a positive way. Positively, challenges make them more steadfast and goal-driven in managing the multigrade schools in Laak North District. Also, empowering them to flourish in society by demonstrating their capacity to positively impact others' lives.

This has been the realization Participant 2-Exodus as he revealed that one thing that keeps him going is to keep himself inspired despite of the challenges. He affirmed:

"...so as a school head so ahm maningkamot ko miskan daghan kayg challenges ah ako nalang gyud ning giharap gyud ang mga challenges para tungod kay na inspire ko sakuan mga bata..." (IDI-2)

Participant 5-Deuteronomy stated:

"Bisan pa man sa mga challenges, na overcome ra man gihapon maski lisod pero na kayanan raman sad noon." (IDI-5)

Certainly, Hurd et al. (2020) conveyed that remaining steadfast in leading and guiding in multigrade schools involves equipping them with the tools for personal accountability, enabling them to tackle life's obstacles. After all, multigrade school teacher-in-charge can still find their true strength and inspiration amidst adversities. Hence, Laouni (2023) stated that these multigrade school teacher-in-charge have the potential to forecast outcomes and yield favorable results in effectively leading a multigrade school. Additionally, it could significantly impact their dedication and perseverance in their work, enhancing their ability to navigate through difficult tasks and stressful situations inherent in school and classroom environments.

Juggling Teaching Preparation and Leadership Duties.

The hardest part of being multigrade school teacher-in-charge when two functions as being a school head and classroom teacher need to do simultaneously. This feels like a roller coaster ride for the multigrade school teacher-in-charge in Laak North District. This clustered theme was conceptualized from the core ideas which are balancing teaching preparation and leadership responsibilities and handling dual responsibilities simultaneously Pertaining to balancing, this entails that the

participants need to do both functions at the same time. This is essential to prevent adverse consequences and promoting effective management and leadership behaviors.

In association with, Participant 1-Genesis honestly shared that it is difficult when preparing both functions to be executed. He asserted:

"Bug-at kay kinahanglan ka mag-prepare sa imong itudlo at the same time nag-lead paka." (IDI-1)

Moreover, Participant 3-Leviticus honestly said:

"Maong usahay gusto nalang ko mag school head kay di na nako matagad ang pagiging teacher sa ka busy sa pagiging school head." (IDI-3)

Based on the finding, being a multigrade school teacher-in-charge is a demanding work. Significantly, Zydziunaite et al. (2020) emphasized that it is necessary to establish and regulate the correlation among multigrade school teacher-in-charge workloads, time management, self-esteem, and leadership, both institutionally and individually. This requires focus to do tasks both as school head and classroom teacher in multigrade schools in Laak North District. Thus, Gamala and Marpa (2022) pointed that these multigrade school teacher-in-charge affect their duties and responsibilities as a school head as part of their managerial skills if they do not do both functions simultaneously. Hence, being designated of two roles needs to be more focused and organized to avoid future problems.

Conclusion and Implications

Summary

This study delved into the lived experiences of multigrade school teacher-in-charge in Laak North District through a using phenomenological study. Further, it unfolded the strategies of multigrade school teacher-in-charge and teachers in addressing the complexities in multigrade schools and came up with a capability training series based on the study's findings.

The study purposely identified five multigrade school teacher-in-charge participants selected based on the inclusion criteria. The participants also willingly subjected themselves to in-depth interviews and focus group discussions using the interview guide protocol and schedule.

The findings of the study were gathered based on the research questions. The results of data analysis generated major themes, clustered themes, and core ideas substantially based on the significant statements of the participants.

Implications

Implications for theory. The findings of this study affirmed Hanson's School Management Theory on Contingency Approach (1979). The theory explained in the context of multigrade schools that the multigrade school teacher-in-charge must understand the situational characteristics of school management in terms of strategic planning, management, and implementation. Consequently, the multigrade school teacher-in-charge could examine how to address the complexities in his/her respective multigrade school.

Implications for Practice. Based on the study's findings, multigrade school teachers can outsource more to address the challenges in multigrade schools. The findings suggest organizing more training series based on the target needs and areas or domains of the multigrade school teacher-in-charge and multigrade teachers. This will help multigrade school teachers capacitate and refine their skills more.

Implications for Future Researchers. This study provides many content and avenues based on its significant findings. Considering these findings, many other areas in the study context yield research gaps that will become the basis for future research endeavors such as conducting it to other division for reliability and confirmation of results. The findings of the study contribute more to understanding the context of multigrade schools.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings and discussion of the study.

Multigrade School Teacher-In-Charge. The multigrade school teacher-in-charge can use this study's capability training series. Based on the concentration of content and the suggested activities of the capability training series, they can also use and apply the capability training series to other multigrade schools.

Multigrade School Teachers. Multigrade teachers can participate in upskilling activities. They can also use the crafted capability training series to cascade and conduct the activities and further enhance their teaching competencies for a multigrade set-up. Also, they can craft research-related undertakings in the context of multigrade teachers.

Department of Education (DepEd). Allow and provide programs for intervention and implementation of projects to address deficiencies and concerns in multigrade schools. This is to establish partnerships with different agencies to aid in the needs

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Competing Interests Statement

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Data Availability Statement

The data used in this research can be accessed through a formal request to the author of the study.

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Appendices

No appendices are included in this article.